

SPACE ASTROMETRY (HIPPARCOS):

Distortion of the detector signal caused by IFOV edges and piloting errors

by L. Lindegren, Lund Observatory (1980 Sept 1)

Summary

The harmonic components of the IDT signal have been computed as functions of the offset position of the IFOV with respect to the stellar image on the photocathode. The computations allow for arbitrary aberrations of the Schmidt-Cassegrain system (telescope) and relay optics, and a circular IFOV with fuzzy edges (radius 15"). Results are shown in Figs. 4 - 11. It is concluded that the tolerance on IFOV piloting is about $\pm 7''$. The results will be used in subsequent simulations to study effects of parasitic stars, etc.

Distortion of the detector signal caused by IFOV edges and piloting errors

by L. Lindegren, Lund Observatory (1980 Sept 1)

1. Introduction

The deterministic detector signal (i.e., disregarding photon noise) is basically characterised by the five signal parameters E_0 (average count rate), M_n (degree of modulation of n :th harmonic, $n=1, 2$), and Δ_n (displacement of n :th harmonic relative some reference phase). Only Δ_n have a direct influence on the measured phase (timing) of the detector signal; the other parameters merely set the statistical accuracy to which the phase can be determined. In presence of instrument aberrations, grid irregularities and other imperfections, the signal parameters will vary across the field of view and with time, but locally (i.e. in a small part of the field and/or during a short time interval) they are still a useful concept.

The signal parameters have previously been evaluated by integrating the modulated intensity immediately behind the grid, or in the stop plane of the relay optics (the latter to take into account grid diffraction and the finite relay optics acceptance angle). In this note the integration is performed in the detector plane (the photocathode), which allows taking into account a finite IFOV (Instantaneous Field Of View) and a possible offset of the IFOV center from the stellar image. The signal parameters have been computed as functions of the IFOV offset angles for the ideal instrument and a few 'typical' combinations of instrumental aberrations (Figs. 4 - 11). Since the computations are based on the approximate Fraunhofer diffraction integral (relating the complex amplitudes in the pupil and image planes by a Fourier transform), it is doubtful whether the results are really more than order-of-magnitude estimates, but it is hoped that they give a qualitatively correct indication of the kind of effects to be expected in reality. The results are particularly relevant to the questions: (1) What are the IFOV piloting tolerances? (2) What happens if there is a second star (parasitic) near the IFOV edges? (3) Is it feasible to detect systematic piloting errors or parasitic stars e.g. by Fourier analysis of the IDT counts (real-time monitoring)? The first question is discussed in Section 4 of this paper, while the other two will be subject to further studies and simulation experiments.

2. Theory

Given the wavenumber $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, the two-dimensional Fourier transform F^+ and its inverse F^- are here defined as follows (integration limits $\pm\infty$ implied):

$$\varphi(\vec{\rho}) = F^+[f(\vec{r})](\vec{\rho}) = \frac{k}{2\pi} \iint f(\vec{r}) \exp(-ik\vec{r}\cdot\vec{\rho}) d\vec{r}, \quad (1)$$

$$f(\vec{r}) = F^-[\varphi(\vec{\rho})](\vec{r}) = \frac{k}{2\pi} \iint \varphi(\vec{\rho}) \exp(ik\vec{r}\cdot\vec{\rho}) d\vec{\rho}. \quad (2)$$

In the Fraunhofer approximation, $f(\vec{r})$ and $\varphi(\vec{\rho})$ may be the complex amplitudes of a quasi-monochromatic light wave in the pupil plane and image plane of an imaging system, respectively; in presence of wavefront aberrations $W(\vec{r})$, the function f should include the factor $\exp[ikW(\vec{r})]$. $\vec{r} = (y, z)$ are linear coordinates in the pupil plane and $\vec{\rho} = (\eta, \zeta)$ are angular coordinates in the image plane. For any two Fourier transform pairs $f \sim \varphi$, $g \sim \gamma$ we have Parseval's identity (the asterisk denoting complex conjugate)

$$\iint f(\vec{r}) g^*(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} = \iint \varphi(\vec{\rho}) \gamma^*(\vec{\rho}) d\vec{\rho} \quad (3)$$

and the convolution theorem

$$\iint f(\vec{r}') g(\vec{r} - \vec{r}') d\vec{r}' = \frac{2\pi}{k} F^-[\varphi(\vec{\rho}) \gamma(\vec{\rho})](\vec{r}), \quad (4)$$

$$\iint \varphi(\vec{\rho}') \gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}') d\vec{\rho}' = \frac{2\pi}{k} F^+[f(\vec{r}) g(\vec{r})](\vec{\rho}). \quad (5)$$

The optical system of Hipparcos is essentially defined by the complex transmittances of three imaging systems: the Schmidt-Cassegrain telescope, the grid plus field lens, and the relay optics. Consequently, the optical function of the instrument is, at least approximately, described by a succession of three Fourier transformations between the following four planes (Fig. 1): (1) the pupil plane containing the entrance pupil of the telescope; (2) the focal plane containing the grid, with the field lens immediately behind; (3) the stop plane at the level of the relay optics, containing an aperture stop to reduce scattered and diffracted light; and (4) the detector plane containing the photocathode of the image dissector.

Coordinates $\vec{r}$, $\vec{\rho}$, $\vec{r}'$, and $\vec{\rho}'$ are defined as in Fig. 1 for the different planes. $\vec{r}$ and $\vec{r}'$ are measured in meters, $\vec{\rho}$ and $\vec{\rho}'$ in radians. The magnification of each stage is (formally) set to unity, so $\vec{r}$ is ideally imaged on $\vec{r}' = \vec{r}$, and $\vec{\rho}$ on $\vec{\rho}' = \vec{\rho}$. The origin of the angular coordinates $\vec{\rho}$ and $\vec{\rho}'$ is taken to be the principal ray from the star under observation; in this co-moving frame;

the star images appear stationary and modulated by the moving grid, and the IFOV is also stationary in the case of perfect piloting.

The direction to the star is defined by the focal plane coordinates of the optical axis (or rather the center of the grid), $\vec{\rho}_0 = (\eta_0, \zeta_0)$. As the instrument spins, η_0 increases roughly uniformly with time, while ζ_0 is nearly constant. The position of the IFOV center with respect to the star image is given by the offset position $\vec{\rho}'_W = (\eta'_W, \zeta'_W)$. The goal is to express the detector signal, E , as a function of star direction $\vec{\rho}_0$ and IFOV offset $\vec{\rho}'_W$, in a way suitable for numerical computations.

Let $T(\vec{r}, \vec{\rho}_0)$ be the complex transmittance of the telescope for a ray passing in direction $\vec{\rho}_0$ through the pupil plane at point $\vec{r}$. (Due to aberrations and since the central obstruction is not in the pupil plane, T is in general a function of both $\vec{r}$ and $\vec{\rho}_0$. However, if only a small part of the field of view is considered, it is convenient to regard $\vec{\rho}_0$ as a parameter rather than an argument, and to suppress it for clarity.) If $a(\vec{r})$ is the complex amplitude of the incident monochromatic and collimated light wave, the complex amplitude in the focal plane is

$$\alpha(\vec{\rho}) = F^+ [a(\vec{r}) T(\vec{r})](\vec{\rho}). \quad (6)$$

Then let $\Gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}_0, \vec{r})$ be the complex transmittance of the grid plus field lens, for a ray passing through the point $\vec{\rho}$ in the focal plane, and in a direction given by its point of origin in the pupil plane, $\vec{r}$. [Again, the dependence on ray direction may be suppressed, this time because the aberrations of the field lens will be neglected. Thus we shall write $\Gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}_0)$. This is the only way $\vec{\rho}_0$ enters the equations.] The complex amplitude of the image of the entrance pupil in the stop plane becomes (using the convolution theorem)

$$\begin{aligned} b(\vec{r}', \vec{\rho}_0) &= F^- [\alpha(\vec{\rho}) \Gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}_0)](\vec{r}') \\ &= \frac{k}{2\pi} \iint F^- [\alpha(\vec{\rho})](\vec{r}) F^- [\Gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}_0)](\vec{r}' - \vec{r}) d\vec{r}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Note that the inverse transform applies because of the reversed axes in the stop plane: $F^- [](\vec{r}') = F^+ [](-\vec{r}')$.

It may be assumed that the grid transmittance is a periodic function of $\eta - \eta_0$ and independent of $\zeta - \zeta_0$. If s is the grid period and field lens aberrations are neglected we have

$$\Gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}_0) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} c_n \exp[-i2\pi n(n - \eta_0)/s], \quad (8)$$

yielding

$$F^{-1}[\Gamma(\vec{\rho} - \vec{\rho}_0)](\vec{r}) = \frac{2\pi}{k} \delta(z) \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} c_n \delta(y - n\lambda/s) \exp(i2\pi n\eta_0/s). \quad (9)$$

$\delta()$ is Dirac's delta function. For an ideal grid with slits of width $s\delta$ ($0 < \delta < 1$) the Fourier coefficients of the grid are

$$c_n = \begin{cases} \delta & \text{for } n = 0, \\ \sin(n\pi\delta)/(n\pi) & \text{for } n \neq 0. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Finite edge sharpness could easily be introduced as an attenuation of the higher-order coefficients; however (10) is sufficiently realistic, for the present purposes, for $|n| \leq 2$.

Putting $a(\vec{r}) \equiv 1$ for the incoming beam, we have from (6), $F^{-1}[\alpha(\vec{\rho})](\vec{r}) = T(\vec{r})$. Inserting this and (9) into (7) we obtain

$$b(\vec{r}', \vec{\rho}_0) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} c_n T(y' - n\lambda/s, z') \exp(i2\pi n\eta_0/s). \quad (11)$$

Thus, the complex amplitude in the stop plane is a periodic function of η_0 , the period being s and the amplitude of the n :th harmonic $c_n T(y' - n\lambda/s, z')$. If $R(\vec{r}')$ is the complex transmittance of the relay optics (dependence on $\vec{\rho}_0$ is again implicit), the complex amplitude of the stellar image on the photocathode is

$$\beta(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}_0) = F^+[b(\vec{r}', \vec{\rho}_0) R(\vec{r}')](\vec{\rho}'). \quad (12)$$

Thanks to the linearity of the transform, this is of course also a periodic function of $\vec{\rho}_0$. However, while b in principle contains an infinite number of harmonics, the aperture in the stop plane only transmits harmonics of order $|n| \leq m \equiv \text{entier}[(1 + \beta)Ds/(2\lambda)]$, if β is the oversizing factor of the stop with respect to the geometrical image of the entrance pupil, and D is the length of the entrance pupil along y . ($\beta = 1$ means that the aperture stop is exactly as long as the geometrical image of the pupil.) The complex amplitude on the photocathode is therefore written

$$\beta(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}_0) = \sum_{n=-m}^m \beta_m(\vec{\rho}') \exp(i2\pi n\eta_0/s), \quad (13)$$

where, according to (12),

$$B_n(\vec{\rho}') = F^+ [c_n T(y' - n\lambda/s, z') R(y', z')] (\vec{\rho}'). \quad (14)$$

Multiplying (13) by its complex conjugate, it is found that the intensity in the detector plane contains only harmonics of order $\leq 2m$, viz.

$$|B(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}'_0)|^2 = \sum_{n=-2m}^{2m} B_n(\vec{\rho}') \exp(i2\pi n\eta_0/s), \quad (15)$$

where

$$B_n(\vec{\rho}') = \sum_j B_j(\vec{\rho}') B_{j-n}^*(\vec{\rho}'). \quad (16)$$

Note that $B_{-n} = B_n^*$, ensuring that (15) is real although the coefficients B_n are in general complex.

While the intensity on the photocathode thus locally may contain harmonics up to order $2m$, it turns out that the integrated intensity in the detector plane only contains those of order $\leq \text{entier}(sD/\lambda)$ ($= m$ for $\beta = 1$). This can be shown by applying (3) on each term of (16):

$$\begin{aligned} \iint B_j(\vec{\rho}') B_{j-n}^*(\vec{\rho}') d\vec{\rho}' &= \\ &= \iint c_j c_{j-n}^* T(y' - j\lambda/s, z') T^*(y' - j\lambda/s + n\lambda/s, z') R(\vec{r}') R^*(\vec{r}') d\vec{r}' = \\ &= 0 \quad \text{for } |n| > sD/\lambda, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

since $T(\vec{r}')$ and $T^*(y' + \Delta, z')$ are non-overlapping for $|\Delta| > D$. With finite IFOV higher harmonics are in principle there, but their amplitudes are very small.

Finally let $\Psi(\vec{\rho}' - \vec{\rho}'_W)$ be the relative quantum efficiency of the photocathode at point $\vec{\rho}'$ while the IFOV center is at position $\vec{\rho}'_W$. The detector signal is then

$$\begin{aligned} E(\vec{\rho}'_0, \vec{\rho}'_W) &= \iint |B(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}'_0)|^2 \Psi(\vec{\rho}' - \vec{\rho}'_W) d\vec{\rho}' \\ &= \sum_{n=-2m}^{2m} E_n(\vec{\rho}'_W) \exp(i2\pi n\eta_0/s), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where

$$E_n(\vec{\rho}'_W) = \iiint B_n(\vec{\rho}') \Psi(\vec{\rho}' - \vec{\rho}'_W) d\vec{\rho}'$$

$$= \frac{2\pi}{k} F^+ \left[F^- [B_n(\vec{\rho}')] (\vec{r}') P(\vec{r}') \right] (\vec{\rho}'_W), \quad (19)$$

$P(\vec{r}')$ being the inverse transform of $\Psi(-\vec{\rho}')$. The signal parameters are finally obtained from the complex amplitudes of the signal harmonics:

$$E_0(\vec{\rho}'_W),$$

$$M_n(\vec{\rho}'_W) \equiv 2|E_n(\vec{\rho}'_W)|/E_0(\vec{\rho}'_W),$$

$$\Delta_n(\vec{\rho}'_W) \equiv \frac{s}{2\pi n} \arg[E_n(\vec{\rho}'_W)], \quad n = 1, 2. \quad (20)$$

Given the functions T and R, which characterise the telescope and relay optics, respectively, for a small part of the field of view; c_n , which characterise the grid; and $P(\vec{r}')$, which characterises the IFOV profile, the computation of the signal parameters is straightforward according to equations (14), (16), (19), and (20), and requires 11 two-dimensional Fourier transformations.

3. Instrument parameters, aberrations and IFOV model

3.1. Fixed parameters

In addition to the IFOV model (Section 3.3) the following parameters are common to all computations described below:

- wavelength:	$\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$
- dimensions of the entrance pupil:	length (along y) $D = 0.25 \text{ m}$ width (along z) 0.10 m obstruction ratio 0.56
- grid parameters:	grid period $s = 1.100 \text{ arcsec}$ slit width $s\delta = 0.396 \text{ arcsec}$
- relay optics oversizing factor:	$\beta = 1.000$
- equivalent focal length:	$f = 2.5 \text{ m}$
- scale factor on photocathode:	$4 \mu\text{m/arcsec}$

3.2. Aberrations of the telescope and relay optics

For the ideal (aberration-free) instrument, the complex transmittances T and R of the telescope and relay optics respectively, are

$$T(\vec{r}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } (|y| > .125) \vee (z < 0) \vee (z > .1) \vee [(0 < z < .056) \wedge (|y - \epsilon| < .07)] \\ 1 & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$R(\vec{r}') = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } (|y| > .125) \vee (z < 0) \vee (z > .1) \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

ϵ is the eccentricity of the pupil, i.e. the displacement of the central obstruction along the y axis. This is due to the obstruction not being in the pupil plane, but approximately 0.75 m behind the pupil; thus $\epsilon \approx 0.75\eta_0 \approx 0.006$ m. The eccentricity is not an aberration in itself, but generates odd (anti-symmetric) aberrations when combined e.g. with a focussing error.

For arbitrary wavefront aberrations $W(\vec{r})$, T and R are multiplied by $\exp[ikW(\vec{r})]$. We shall consider only three kinds of aberration: defocussing, and a coma-like wavefront error of third or fifth order.

Defocussing, corresponding to a displacement of the grid by Δx , generates the wavefront error

$$W(\vec{r}) = \frac{\Delta x}{2f^2} |\vec{r}|^2 \quad (23)$$

where $f = 2.5$ m is the equivalent focal length of the telescope. A reasonable value is $\Delta x = 10$ μm for telescope defocussing. The same formula (23) holds for the relay optics (with $\vec{r}'$ in place of $\vec{r}$). Here, it is more convenient to express the focus error as the radius of the geometrical blur 'circle', which is $\approx \Delta x D / (2f^2)$ radians. According to the MATRA Report (60/890, Jan 1980), the blur radius is typically 20 - 40 μm on the photocathode, or 5 - 10 arcsec; adopting 8 arcsec blur radius, we have $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm for the relay optics. (This assuming that longitudinal chromatism is the dominating aberration.)

The usual classification of third and higher order aberrations is largely irrelevant in the case of the Hipparcos instrument, because of its asymmetric pupil, rectangular shape, high obstruction ratio, and (in particular) the one-dimensionality of the grid, which means that the ζ component of transverse aberrations are relatively unimportant. For the present application it is perhaps more relevant to consider in the first instance only wavefront errors which are independent of the z coordinate, i.e. polynomials in y . With respect

to the present rectangular pupil (obstruction ratio 0.56), the first five orthonormal polynomials in $u = 2y/D$ (normalised y coordinate) are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_0(u) &= 1 \\
 p_1(u) &= 1.511 u \\
 p_2(u) &= -1.454 + 3.321 u^2 \\
 p_3(u) &= -4.163 u + 6.456 u^3 \\
 p_4(u) &= 1.423 - 11.167 u^2 + 12.276 u^4 \\
 p_5(u) &= 7.489 u - 30.193 u^3 + 25.456 u^5.
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

The orthonormality means that $\langle p_i p_j \rangle = \delta_{ij}$, if $\langle \rangle$ denotes averaging over the pupil. The rms wavefront error of $W(\vec{r}) = \sum_j w_j p_j(2y/D)$ is $(w_2^2 + w_3^2 + \dots)^{1/2}$. p_0 and p_1 are uninteresting; p_2 may represent defocus and/or astigmatism and p_4 spherical aberration; the coma-like components p_3 and p_5 are the most interesting ones, as they produce image shifts which depend on both spatial frequency and wavelength. In view of the overall wavefront error tolerances (about $\lambda/20$; cf. MATRA Report), it appears realistic to set $w_3 = 20$ nm or $w_5 = 20$ nm in order to study the effects of coma in the telescope. For the relay optics $w_3 \approx 150$ nm is perhaps more representative.

The following eight cases have been studied:

ϵ	telescope (T)			relay (R)		Fig.
	Δx	w_3	w_5	Δx	w_3	
0 mm	0.00 mm	0	0	0.00 mm	0	4
0	0.00	0	0	1.92	0	5
0	0.00	0	0	1.92	$\lambda/3$	6
6.0	0.00	0	0	1.92	0	7
0	0.01	0	0	1.92	0	8
6.0	0.01	0	0	1.92	0	9
0	0.00	$\lambda/25$	0	1.92	0	10
0	0.00	0	$\lambda/25$	1.92	0	11

3.3. IFOV model

The IFOV response function $\Psi(\vec{\rho}')$ is nominally a circular area of radius $\Theta = 15$ arcsec, with unity sensitivity inside and zero outside this radius. Its Fourier transform is

$$P_o(\vec{r}) = \frac{k}{2\pi} \pi\Theta^2 \frac{2J_1(k\Theta|\vec{r}'|)}{k\Theta|\vec{r}'|}, \quad (25)$$

where J_1 is the Bessel function of first kind and order 1. A more realistic model is obtained by convolving with a suitable circular-symmetric point spread function PSF, which in the simplest case may be the two-dimensional gaussian of width σ , $PSF = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-1} \exp[-|\vec{\rho}'|^2/(2\sigma^2)]$. Since a gaussian PSF usually underestimates the power in the far wings, it may be safer (when the wings are important) to assume a PSF which is the two-dimensional equivalent of the Lorentz function (Cauchy distribution), $PSF = (2\pi\mu^2)^{-1} (1 + |\vec{\rho}'|^2/\mu^2)^{-3/2}$, where μ is a characteristic width. The Fourier transform of Ψ becomes

$$P(\vec{r}) = P_o(\vec{r}) \cdot \begin{cases} \exp(-k^2\sigma^2|\vec{r}'|^2/2) & \text{(gaussian PSF)} \\ \exp(-k\mu|\vec{r}'|) & \text{(lorentzian PSF)} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

The two models are compared with data from the manufacturer (ITT) in Fig. 2. Resolution (which depends on Θ and σ or μ) is usually given as percent amplitude modulation at one or several spatial frequencies, measured by means of a square wave bar chart. The theoretical resolution with the present IFOV models is

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \% \text{ amplitude} \\ \text{modulation} \end{array} \right) = 400 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(\pi n/2)}{\pi n} \frac{2J_1(2\pi n\Theta/s)}{2\pi n\Theta/s} \cdot \begin{cases} \exp[-(2\pi n/s)^2/2] \\ \exp(-2\pi n/s) \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

in which s is the period of the bar chart. With $4 \mu\text{m}/\text{arcsec}$ on the photocathode, $s = 12700/(\text{TV lines per inch})$ arcsec. Fig. 2 indicates that $\sigma = 2$ arcsec (0.32 mil) or $\mu = 1$ arcsec (0.16 mil) are reasonable figures, at least at field center. The corresponding response functions $\Psi(\vec{\rho}')$ are shown in Fig. 3.

Another estimate of σ and μ results from the measured 'Rise Distance', which is about 10-15 μm for the F4012 IDT with improved coil assembly (ITT report by R. Hertel, August 20, 1974). If 'Rise Distance' is interpreted as the distance from 10% to 90% of maximum sensitivity, this corresponds to $\sigma = 1-1.5$ arcsec or $\mu = 0.5-0.8$ arcsec.

In view of all this, it is believed that the adopted IFOV model, $\Theta = 15$ arcsec and $\mu = 1$ arcsec (Fig. 3b), is rather conservative.

3.4. Concerning the computations

The two-dimensional Fourier transformations were performed on a grid of 128×64 points, using the FFT algorithm. One pixel corresponds to $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ in the pupil and stop planes and $0.40286 \times 0.80572 \text{ arcsec}^2$ in the focal and detector planes. The aliasing period in Figs. 4-11 is therefore about 51.6 arcsec, slightly more than the displayed area. This should be remembered, especially when interpreting the displacement plots (Δ_n), which appear to be badly affected by aliasing for $\ln'_w | \gtrsim 20 \text{ arcsec}$.

4. Results and conclusions: IFOV piloting tolerance

First of all it is worth noticing that even the aberration-free instrument (Fig. 4) produces some distortion of the IDT signal, apart from the decreased average count rate (E_0), when the IFOV is not centered on the stellar image. However, the distortion is practically negligible unless the IFOV is offset by about $15''$ or more.

In general it can be said that the amplitudes of the signal harmonics (E_0 , M_1 , M_2) are mostly determined by the aberrations of the relay optics, while their displacements (Δ_1 , Δ_2) depend on the aberrations of the telescope. In particular, even very strongly comatic relay optics (Fig. 6) do not produce displacements appreciably greater than those obtained already with the perfect instrument. On the other hand, Δ_1 is very sensitive to coma of the telescope (Figs. 10-11).

In all cases there is however an area (approximately $7''$ radius), in which the amplitudes and displacements are constant to within 5 % and 1 milliarcsec, respectively. Thus, the simple relation applies: (max. tolerable IFOV offset, $7''$) $\approx$ (IFOV radius, $15''$) - (geometrical blur radius of relay optics, $8''$).

Fig. 1. Definition of coordinates at various stages of the optical system. Linear coordinates (y, z) and (y', z') are defined in the pupil and stop planes with origins at the optical axis (o.a.). In the focal plane and detector plane, angular coordinates (η, ζ) and (η', ζ') are defined having origins at the principal ray (p.r.) from the star in question. The instantaneous direction to the star is given by the focal plane coordinates of the o.a., (η_0, ζ_0) . The position of the IFOV is given by its offset position with respect to the p.r., (η'_W, ζ'_W) . The length of the entrance pupil (e.p.) along the y axis is D ; that of the aperture stop (in the stop plane) is βD , β being the relay optics oversizing factor (here, $\beta = 1$).

Fig. 2. The solid curves show the theoretical square-wave response of an image dissector tube with a circular aperture (IFOV) of diameter 0.001 inch (1 mil), and with various degrees of edge fuzziness as resulting from a gaussian (top) or lorentzian (bottom) point spread function (PSF). σ and μ are the characteristic widths of the gaussian and lorentzian PSF, respectively.

The dashed curve is the 'Typical VIDISSECTOR Image Dissector Resolution for ITT Types F4011, F4012 and F4052' with a 0.001 inch diameter aperture, according to the manufacturer. The vertical bars indicate the typical resolution at 1000 and 1600 TVL/inch according to manufacturer's data sheet (F4012 and F4012RP tubes with F4532 deflection assembly), viz. 60 and 20 % modulation at field center, and 40 and 10 % modulation at edge of field.

Fig. 3a. IFOV model with gaussian PSF (point spread function) of standard width $\sigma = 2''$, corresponding to $8 \mu\text{m}$ or 0.32 mil on the photocathode. Contours are given for 1, 10, 50, 80, 90, 95, 98, 99, and 99.5 % of maximum response. This IFOV model is not used in subsequent computations.

Fig. 3b. The adopted IFOV model with a Lorentzian PSF of width $\mu = 1''$ ($4 \mu\text{m}$ or 0.16 mil on the photocathode). Contours are at 10, 50, 80, 90, 95, 98, 99, and 99.5 % of maximum response.

Explanation to Figs. 4 - 11

Each of the following eight figures gives the five signal parameters and the diffraction image in the detector plane for a certain combination of telescope and relay optics aberrations, indicated by the legend below the figure. Each contour plot covers an area of $50 \times 50 \text{ arcsec}^2$ centered on the principal ray. The disposition is as follows:

$E_0(\vec{\rho}'_W)$, normalized

Average count rate as function of IFOV offset $\vec{\rho}'_W$, normalized to 100 % at maximum.

Contour levels:

100 99.5 99 98 95 90 80 50 10%

$B_0(\vec{\rho}')$, normalized

Average intensity in the detector plane, normalized to unity at maximum intensity.

Contour levels: $-^{10}\log(I/I_{\max}) =$
0 0.5 1 2 3 4 5 6

$M_1(\vec{\rho}'_W)$

Percent modulation of the first harmonic of the detector signal.

Contour levels:

multiples of 5%

$\Delta_1(\vec{\rho}'_W)$

Displacement of the first harmonic, in milliarcsec.

Contour levels:

multiples of 1 milliarcsec

$M_2(\vec{\rho}'_W)$

Percent modulation of the second harmonic of the detector signal.

Contour levels:

multiples of 2%

$\Delta_2(\vec{\rho}'_W)$

Displacement of the second harmonic, in milliarcsec.

Contour levels:

multiples of 1 milliarcsec

Fig. 4. telescope aberrations: none
 relay optics aberrations: none

Fig. 5. telescope aberrations: none
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm

Fig. 6. telescope aberrations: none
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm, 3rd-order 'coma', rms wavefront error $w_3 = \lambda/3$

Fig. 7. telescope aberrations: none, but central obstruction displaced $\epsilon = 6.0$ mm
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm

Fig. 8. telescope aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 0.01$ mm
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm

Fig. 9. telescope aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 0.01$ mm, and central obstruction displaced $\epsilon = 6.0$ mm
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm

Fig. 10. telescope aberrations: 3rd-order 'coma', rms wavefront error $w_3 = \lambda/25$
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm

Fig. 11. telescope aberrations: 5th-order 'coma', rms wavefront error $w_5 = \lambda/25$
 relay optics aberrations: defocus $\Delta x = 1.92$ mm